

Key resource table

RESOURCE TYPE	RESOURCE NAME	SOURCE	IDENTIFIER	NEW/ REUSE
Antibodies	Anti-pS65-Ubiquitin	Cell Signaling Technology	62802 RRID:AB_2799632	Reuse
Antibodies	Anti- PINK1 (D8G3)	Cell Signaling Technology	6946S RRID:AB_11179069	Reuse
Antibodies	Anti-ATF4	Cell Signaling Technology	11815S RRID:AB_2616025	Reuse
Antibodies	Anti-HSP60	Cell Signaling Technology	4870S RRID:AB_2295614	Reuse
Antibodies	Anti- GAPDH (6C5)	Santa Cruz	sc-32233 RRID:AB_627679	Reuse
Antibodies	Anti-OPA1	BD biosciences	612607 RRID:AB_399889	Reuse
Antibodies	Anti-Rabbit IgG (H+L), HRP Conjugate	Thermo Fisher Scientific	31460 RRID:AB_228341	Reuse
Antibodies	Anti-Mouse IgG (H+L), HRP Conjugate	Thermo Fisher Scientific	31450 RRID:AB_228427	Reuse
Chemicals	Gamitrinib TPP	MedChemExpress	HY-102007	Reuse
Chemicals	MitoSpy Red CMXRos	BioLegend	424801	Reuse
Chemicals	Hoechst 33342	Invitrogen	R37605	Reuse
Chemicals	Oligomycin A	Sigma-Aldrich	75351	Reuse
Chemicals	Antimycin A	Sigma-Aldrich	A8674	Reuse
Chemicals	Oligomycin A	Sigma-Aldrich	75351	Reuse
Chemicals	Antimycin A	Sigma-Aldrich	A8674	Reuse
Chemicals	PhosSTOP™	Merck	4906845001	Reuse
Chemicals	Phosphatase Inhibitor Cocktail 2	Sigma-Aldrich	P5726	Reuse
Chemicals	cOplete™ EDTA-free Protease Inhibitor Cocktail	Merck	11873580001	Reuse
Chemicals	2-Chloroacetamide	Sigma-Aldrich	C0267	Reuse
Chemicals	Halo-Link Resin	Promega	G1913	Reuse
Chemicals	GFP-Agarose	MRC PPU Products & Reagents	DU61915Agarose	Reuse
Chemicals	Clarity Western ECL Substrate	Biorad	1705061	Reuse
Critical commercial assays	Pierce™ BCA Protein Assay Kits	Biorad	1705061	Reuse
Critical commercial assays	Cell Viability Assay	Thermo Fisher Scientific	23227	Reuse
Recombinant protein	His-Halo-multiDSK	MRC PPU Products & Reagents	DU55458	Reuse

cDNA constructs	PINK1 Nter KI Sense B Guide + PURO	MRC PPU Products & Reagents	DU64062	Reuse
cDNA constructs	PINK1 Nter KI Antisense B Guide + Cas9n	MRC PPU Products & Reagents	DU64072	Reuse
cDNA constructs	pMA PINK1 Nter cDNA c-GFP pA donor	MRC PPU Products & Reagents	DU64119	Reuse
cDNA constructs	pET21d vector + HSPD1	Parnas et al. (1)	Addgene: 250362	Reuse
cDNA constructs	pET22b(+) vector + Hsp10	Nisemblat et al. (2)	Addgene: 250361	Reuse
Datesets	39S mitochondrial ribosome, cryo-ET STA from HeLa	This study	EMDB: 55203	New
Datesets	55S mitochondrial ribosome, cryo-ET STA from HeLa	This study	EMDB: 55204	New
Datesets	mtHsp60 single-ring complex, cryo-ET STA from HeLa	This study	EMDB: 55205	New
Datesets	mtHsp60:mtHsp10 half-football complex, cryo-ET STA from HeLa	This study	EMDB: 55206	New
Datesets	mtHsp60:mtHsp10 football, cryo-ET STA from HeLa	This study	EMDB: 55207	New
Datesets	ATP-bound human mtHsp60:mtHsp10 football complex (D7), SPA reconstruction	This study	EMDB: 54898 PDB: 9SHG	New
Datesets	ATP-bound human mtHsp60:mtHsp10 half-football complex (C7), SPA reconstruction	This study	EMDB: 54900 PDB: 9SHI	New
Datesets	ATP-bound human mtHsp60:mtHsp10 bullet complex (C7), SPA reconstruction	This study	EMDB: 54899 PDB: 9SHH	New
Datesets	ATP-bound human mtHsp60:mtHsp10 double-ring Datesets complex (C7), SPA reconstruction	This study	EMDB: 54901 PDB: 9SHJ	New
Datesets	ATP-bound human mtHsp60:mtHsp10 single-ring complex (C7), SPA reconstruction	This study	EMDB: 54903 PDB: 9SHL	New
Datesets	ADP-bound human mtHsp60:mtHsp10 single-ring complex (C7), SPA reconstruction	This study	EMDB: 54902 PDB: 9SHK	New

Datesets	In situ cryo-ET dataset of mitochondria in HeLa cells	This study	EMPIAR-13145	New
Datesets	SPA dataset of in vitro human mHsp60 assemblies	This study	EMPIAR- 13154	New
Datesets	Output atomic models from MDFF	This study	https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.5283/EPUB.78309	New
Datesets	Fluorescence images of G-TPP time-course	This study	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17699821	New
Datesets	SDS PAGE and Western-blot images	This study	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17700140	New
Datesets	Data of quantifications in Fig. 1C, D and 2B, E, H	This study	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17698986	New
Cell lines	HeLa PINK1-GFP knock-in cell line	This study	Cellosaurus: CVCL_F1H5	New
Software/code	Relion v4.0	Kimanius et al. (3)	RRID: SCR_016274 https://doi.org/10.1042/bcj20210708 https://github.com/3dem/relion/tree/ver4.0	Reuse
Software/code	CryoSPARC	Structura Biotechnology Inc.	RRID: SCR_016501 https://cryosparc.com	Reuse
Software/code	M/WARP v.1.0.9	Tegunov et al. (4)	RRID: SCR_018071 https://doi.org/10.1038/s41592-020-01054-7 https://github.com/cramerlab/warp	Reuse
Software/code	MotionCorr v2.1	Zheng et al. (5)	RRID: SCR_016499 https://doi.org/10.1038/nmeth.4193	Reuse
Software/code	Phenix 1.21.2	Liebschner et al. (6)	RRID: SCR_014224 https://doi.org/10.1107/s2059798319011471 https://phenix-online.org/	Reuse
Software/code	Coot 0.9.2	Emsley et al. (7)	RRID: SCR_014222 https://doi.org/10.1107/s0907444910007493 https://www2.mrc-lmb.cam.ac.uk/personal/pemsley/coot/	Reuse
Software/code	IMOD v4.11	Kremer et al. (8)	RRID: SCR_003297 https://doi.org/10.1006/jsbi.1996.0013 https://bio3d.colorado.edu/imod/index.html	Reuse
Software/code	Dynamo 1.1.452	Castaño-Diez et al. (9)	RRID: SCR_025592 https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsb.2011.12.017 https://www.dynamo-em.org/w/index.php?title=Downloads	Reuse
Software/code	DeepFinder v0.0.1	Moebel et al. (10)	https://doi.org/10.1038/s41592-021-01275-4 https://github.com/deep-finder/cryoet-deepfinder	Reuse
Software/code	UCSF ChimeraX	Goddard et al. (11)	RRID: SCR_015872 https://doi.org/10.1002/pro.3235 https://www.rbvi.ucsf.edu/chimerax/	Reuse

Software/ code	ArtiaX	Ermel et al. (12)	https://doi.org/10.1002/pro.4472 https://github.com/FrangakisLab/ArtiaX	Reuse
Software/ code	Serial EM software	Mastronarde (13)	RRID: SCR_017293 https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsb.2005.07.007 https://bio3d.colorado.edu/SerialEM/	Reuse
Software/ code	PACEtomo	Eisenstein et al. (14)	https://doi.org/10.1038/s41592-022-01690-1 https://github.com/eisfabian/PACEtomo	Reuse
Software/ code	AutoTEM 5 software	Thermo Fisher Scientific	https://www.thermofisher.com/de/de/home/electron-microscopy/products/software-em-3d-vis/autotem-5-software.html	Reuse
Software/ code	EPU	Thermo Fisher Scientific	https://www.thermofisher.com/es/es/home/electron-microscopy/products/software-em-3d-vis/epu-software.html	Reuse
Software/ code	Amira v 2021.2	Thermo Fisher Scientific	RRID: SCR_007353 https://www.thermofisher.com/de/de/home/electron-microscopy/products/software-em-3d-vis/amira-software.html	Reuse
Software/ code	MATLAB R2019b	MathWorks	RRID: SCR_001622	Reuse
Software/ code	LAS X	Leica Microsystems	RRID: SCR_013673	Reuse
Software/ code	MemBrain-seg	Lamm et al. (15)	https://doi.org/10.1101/2024.01.05.574336 https://github.com/teamtomo/membrain-seg	Reuse
Software/ code	Dragonfly v2022.2	Comet technologies	RRID: SCR_025150 https://dragonfly.comet.tech/en/products/dragonfly-3d-world	Reuse
Software/ code	IsoNet v0.2	Liu et al. (16)	https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-022-33957-8 https://github.com/IsoNet-cryoET/IsoNet	Reuse
Software/ code	TOMOMAN v0.9	Khavnekar et al. (17)	https://doi.org/10.1101/2024.05.02.589639 https://github.com/wan-lab-vanderbilt/TOMOMAN	Reuse
Software/ code	Violin Plots for Matlab	Bechtold (18)	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4559846	Reuse
Software/ code	PROCMan in-house scripts	This study	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17292570	New
Software/ code	MuRePP in-house scripts	This study	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17292570	New
Protocols	Protein expression and purification	Weiss et al. (19)	https://doi.org/10.1016/bs.mie.2024.07.049	Reuse
Protocols	Sample preparation for single-particle cryo-EM	Chen et al. (20)	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.xpro.2020.100278	Reuse
Protocols	Data collection for single-particle cryo-EM	Murillo, Suarez (21)	https://dx.doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io.14egn3m5ql5d/v1	Reuse
Protocols	Cryo-EM data processing and 3D reconstruction	Dilorio, Kulczyk (22)	https://doi.org/10.3791/63387	Reuse

Protocols	Fluorescence microscopy	BioLegend	https://d1spbj2x7qk4bg.cloudfront.net/fr-ch/products/mitospy-red-cmxros-13890?displayInline=true&filename=MitoSpy%E2%84%A2%20Red%20CMXRos.pdf&leftRightMargin=15&pdf=true&topBottomMargin=15&v=20251202073748	Reuse
Protocols	Cryo-ET sample preparation	Zhao (23)	https://dx.doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io.261ge5pxyg47/v1	Reuse
Protocols	Cell thinning by focused ion beam-scanning electron microscopy (FIB/SEM)	Hutchings et al. (24)	https://dx.doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io.kqdg3xpyqg25/v3	Reuse
Protocols	Cryo-ET data collection	Hutchings et al. (25)	https://dx.doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io.6qpvr3442vmk/v1	Reuse
Protocols	Deep Learning-Based Segmentation	Heebner et al. (26)	https://doi.org/10.3791/64435	Reuse
Protocols	Ubiquitin capture using Halo-m-DSK	Wilson et al. (27)	https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0046398	Reuse
Protocols	Cell viability assay	Promega	https://www.promega.de/-/media/files/resources/protocols/technical-manuals/101/celltiterglo-2-0-assay-protocol.pdf?rev=2a68347929f049afa3ff8a3b68ae7f6d&sc_lang=en	Reuse
Protocols	Generation of HeLa PINK1-GFP knock-in cell line using CRISPR/Cas9	Snelling, Muqit (28)	https://dx.doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io.dm6gpm38pgzp/v1	Reuse
Protocols	Whole-cell lysate preparation	Antico, Muqit (29)	https://dx.doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io.bswanfae	Reuse
Protocols	GFP-PINK1 immunoprecipitation and immunoblotting	Pal et al. (30)	https://dx.doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io.eq2ly7kxqlx9/v1	Reuse
Protocols	Molecular dynamics flexible fitting (MDFF)	Trabuco et al. (31)	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ymeth.2009.04.005	Reuse
Others	R2/2 UltraAuFoil gold-film mesh 200 gold EM grids	Quantifoil	N/A	Reuse
Others	Autogrid support with cutout	Thermo Fisher Scientific	N/A	Reuse
Others	Vitrobot Mark IV	Thermo Fisher Scientific	N/A	Reuse
Others	Aquilos 2 FIB/SEM	Thermo Fisher Scientific	N/A	Reuse
Others	Titan Krios G4	Thermo Fisher Scientific	N/A	Reuse

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